

H2020-FNR-2020-2
LC-FNR-13-2020

**CREATING ADDED-VALUE CHEMICALS FROM BIO-INDUSTRIAL CO₂
EMISSIONS USING INTEGRATED CATALYTIC TECHNOLOGIES**

**D7.2 – Dissemination and
Communication Plan
(Yearly update from M1 to M30)**

Lead Contractor: Sustainable Innovations (SIE)

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Date: 31/10/2023

This document corresponds to D7.2 and describes the Communication and Dissemination Plan (contract no. 101000580) to be adopted by the CATCO2NVERS project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, models and simulation tools, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to the appropriate target communities.

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CATCO2NVERS

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Website	https://catco2nvers.eu/		

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1 Executive summary

This document contains a detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan that outlines the project's audiences, and communication channels for dissemination. It also answers the questions WHO? WHAT? WHEN? HOW? and provides an integrated, accurate, and efficient dissemination strategy. In addition, it highlights potential audiences, roles and responsibilities, and methods of communication to be used for the CATCO2NVERS tool promotion.

Task 7.1 aims at proactively promoting the CATCO2NVERS project and its results by providing targeted information to various audiences. The promotion activities will be part of the dissemination and communication plan, and this document presents the first step in achieving the partial objective.

2 Acronyms and abbreviations

BIOR	Bio-refineries
CD	Catalyst developers
DCP	Dissemination and communication plan
DoA	Description of Activities
FDME	Furan Dicarboxylic Methyl Ester
FME	Furfural Methyl Ester
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Public
IP	Intellectual Property
KER	Key exploitable result
NADH	Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide
RPMCA	Regulators, Policy Makers & Community Associations
SC	Scientific Community
SIE	Sustainable Innovations Europe
TD	Technology developers
WP	Work package

3 Introduction

This document describes the Communication and Dissemination Plan to be adopted by the CATCO₂NVERS project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, models and simulation tools, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to the appropriate target communities.

It, first of all, presents the objectives of the communication and dissemination plan, the main target audiences to follow with the tools and channels. Within these tools and channels, different means and platforms, such as the website, the social media channels, printed materials, newsletters, press releases, scientific journals, and trade media are explored. In addition, it is also commented the participation in conferences, workshops, and events. The stakeholders' engagement is also explored, to then proceed to evaluate which indicators and targets are set to evaluate the communication efforts.

The communication and dissemination will involve different levels (European level, international level, regional level, etc.) and it will work both externally and internally. These realms are also considered in the plan below.

A timeline with the main three communication phases is presented, to finish with an overview of the actions carried out from M1 to M6.

3.1 Context of WP7

The main objective of this WP is to maximise the impact of the project results during its lifetime and after the project's end. More in detail, the specific objectives are:

- To disseminate the project results among relevant industrial and academic stakeholders.
- To raise awareness among the public about the potential of using CO₂ utilisation technologies coupled to bio-based industries.
- To map and evaluate the market size of CATCO₂NVERS technologies and products within the EU bio-economy.
- To design novel and effective business models to enhance economic profitability of bio-based industries while reducing CO₂ emissions.

- To ensure the exploitation of the project's KER through adequate exploitation plans.

3.2 Objectives of T7.1

The DoA contemplates that a detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan should be produced at the beginning of the project (M6), based on the preliminary indications given in Section 2.2. and in collaboration with all the consortium; this plan will outline the project's audiences, and communication channels for dissemination. It will provide an integrated, accurate, and efficient dissemination strategy, highlight the potential audiences, roles and responsibilities, and methods of communication to be used. The first list of stakeholders and end-users will be prepared at month 6, to be updated during the project lifetime to include all relevant actors in consultations devoted to better explore the local context and adapt the technologies. The involvement of stakeholders from the beginning of the project will be crucial to raise awareness about related problems and to enhance the community's acceptance of the proposed efficient exploitation strategies.

4 Objectives of the DCP

The main objective of the CATCO₂NVERS dissemination strategy is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, models and simulation tools, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to appropriate target communities. It is anticipated that contributors to CATCO₂NVERS development, evaluation, market uptake, and exploitation are identified and motivated to proactively participate.

A multistep and multichannel approach will be used in the CATCO₂NVERS dissemination strategy in order to reach and engage different stakeholders and target groups with adjusted information for needs and interests. Awareness will be raised to all possible project beneficiaries.

The key specific objectives to achieve the CATCO₂NVERS goals are:

- To disseminate the project results among relevant industrial and academic stakeholders.
- To raise awareness among the public about the potential of using CO₂ utilisation technologies coupled to bio-based industries.
- To build a strong network of stakeholders interested in the project results

- To ensure effective knowledge transfer of CATCO2NVERS outcomes,

5 Target audiences

CATCO2NVERS has preliminarily identified a significant list of stakeholders to which the dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed

Table 5.1: Target groups & contents

TARGET GROUP / STAKEHOLDER	TARGETED RESULTS/ CONTENT
Bio-refineries (BIOR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of their emissions & integration of CO₂ in their processes • Synergies between industry sectors • Modelling of decentralized pre-treatment, new processes • Additional yields through carbon conversion technology integration.
Catalyst developers (CD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of new bi-functional heterogeneous catalysts based on organic/inorganic supports • Development of novel immobilized biocatalysts
Technology developers (TD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel route to lactic acid from CO₂ and bioethanol feedstocks • CO₂ conversion to FDME from Furfural - two-step one-pot process • Models for flexible facilities
Regulators, Policy Makers & Community Associations (RPMCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New resources available through the integration of carbon conversion technology in the bio-based industries and its application potential • Potential of carbon conversion technology and advancements for the circular bioeconomy • Need for further scientific research
Scientific Community (SC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results on novel system for production Lactic acid from CO₂ and ethanol • Results on novel NADH regeneration methods • Logistics modelling of bio-based streams in decentralized system, different feedstocks & circularity assessment of bio-CO₂ based products

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synthesis and characterization of new bi-functional heterogeneous catalysts based on porous organic polymers • Synthesis and oxidative esterification of furfural to obtain furfural methyl ester (FME) in soft conditions • Carboxylation of FME with CO₂ to obtain FDME in soft conditions • Furfural to FDME using CO₂ by a two-steps one-pot process
General Public (GP).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the development of a new technology that allows the use of CO₂ to obtain a precursor of bioplastics • New resources without land-use change or food/feed controversy, CO₂ as feedstock, connection to climate change, • Circular economy concept

Several key stakeholders have been already detected by consortium partners, such as Turkish Cosmetics Manufacturers and Researchers Association (Küad), Turkish Quality Association (Kalder), Istanbul Chamber of Industry - European Enterprise Network, Sarten Packaging, Iff (International Flavors & Fragrances Inc), Parkim Group, Sfa Arge, Antimikrop Lab, Plastic Move; and others.

Trade media have already been identified as well: Technology Review, Popular Mechanics, Technology Review, Engineering & Technology, RQ Magazine, Ingenieur, Horizon Magazine, Innovators Magazine, Econoticas, RETEMA, Industria Ambiente and others.

Likewise, similar European projects have been identified to search for synergies such as CO2SMOS, CO2PERATE, eCOCO2 or BIOCON-CO2.

6 Tools and channels

Different tools and channels will be used to disseminate and communicate the activities carried out by CATCO2NVERS and its results. Each tool and channel will be used appropriately to address different target groups at different stages of the proposal implementation, thereby increasing the efficiency of the DCP. The relationship between the tools and channels, the target groups, and the expected results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6.1: Channels / Tools / Target groups/ Expected impacts

Channels	Tools	Target Groups	Expected Results
Printed Materials	Brochure	Industry, Academia, Manufacturers, End consumers, Associations, Environmental Organisations, Standardisation bodies and policy makers	Inform about the project scope, objectives, impacts, methodology and results.
	Leaflet		
Online	CATCO2NVERS project website	Scientific community, industry, technology developers, G.Public	(1) Inform about the project scope, objectives, impacts, methodology and results. (2) Keep the audience updated with regular news. (3) Share the public deliverables. (4) Raise awareness on the project technologies.
	Social Media (Twitter & LinkedIn)		
	Videos		
	Newsletters		
	Press Releases	All target groups/ stakeholders	Inform about the project scope, objectives, impacts, methodology and results.
		Media groups and journalists/ General public	Raise awareness among on the economic and environmental impacts of the project.
Publications	Scientific Publications	Industry, Academia, Manufacturers, End consumers, Associations, Environmental Organisations	To raise awareness on the economic and environmental impacts of the project.
Events (Organized)	Workshop		
	Webinars	Standardisation bodies & policy makers	To persuade on the benefits resulting from an uptake of CATCO2NVERS innovations.
Events (Attended)	Workshops	Industry, Academia, Manufacturers, End consumers, Associations, Environmental Organisations	To communicate the results obtained. To share the capacities acquired and encourage replication and exploitation.
	Conferences		
	Tradeshows		

Several dissemination tools and channels will be used, including a project website, articles targeted at both a lay and a technical audience, press releases, e-newsletters, scientific papers and leaflets, social media presence, and participation in workshops/conferences.

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Any dissemination activities and publications in the project, including the project website, will specify that the project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, as well as displaying the European emblem. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem will be given appropriate prominence. All publications will reference the grant agreement number.

The communication activities within the project are both periodic (management group meetings, newsletters, project group meetings, and reporting to the commission) and online (project restricted area on the website).

Communication activities to stakeholders outside the project group are based on the dissemination plan presented in section 2.2 of the Grant Agreement. The journal articles are primarily intended to communicate the recent findings to the scientific and academic communities. However, the project will also publish in trade journals and magazines important to the industry to disseminate new relevant solutions to other possible end-users. Project presentations at technical conferences are intended to reach the same audience.

6.1 Project identity

A recognisable project identity was developed to build a visual brand and ultimately offer a package of templates that will facilitate the building of notoriety progressively through the project. This includes creating a project logo and an accompanying style guide. These will be consistently used for the project website and all other communication templates, such as PowerPoint, Word, posters, and EC Reports : <https://catco2nvers.eu/documents/>

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Image 6.1: Brand guidelines

Brand Guidelines

Color palette

#0070C0	#00A08A	#004020	#006040	#008060	#004020	#006040	#008060	#00A08A	#0070C0
R 255	R 160	R 0	R 141	R 141	R 0	R 42	R 0	R 0	R 15
G 205	G 180	G 255	G 40	G 200	G 0	G 155	G 174	G 150	G 0
B 205	B 110	B 0	B 40	B 40	B 0	B 114	B 0	B 102	B 15

Text/background/icon

#0070C0	#00A08A	#004020
R 255	R 160	R 0
G 205	G 180	G 255
B 205	B 110	B 0

Background/graphic elements

Font setting print & desktop presentation

Title 1 Bold 24pt
Century Gothic #0070C0 Abcdefghi

Subtitle 1 Regular 16pt
Century Gothic #00A08A Abcdefghi

Title 3 Bold 12pt
Century Gothic #004020 Abcdefghi

Text Regular 11pt
Century Gothic #0070C0 Abcdefghi

Figures Regular Italic 11pt
Century Gothic #00A08A Abcdefghi

Font setting web (Google font)

Montserrat #0070C0 Abcdefghi

Montserrat #00A08A Abcdefghi

Montserrat #004020 Abcdefghi

Montserrat #0070C0 Abcdefghi

Montserrat #00A08A Abcdefghi

Iconography style

Photography style

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6.2 Project website

CATCO2NVERS has been given an up-to-date and user-friendly project website (<https://catco2nvers.eu/>) It will be the primary source of information for external parties, providing updates on project activities and achievements to all target audiences. The website aims to inform the scientific community and associated industries about project developments, but also to present the project's achievements and novel pilot lines to the public.

All partners will contribute to the website by providing relevant project information in accessible language (laymen's terms). All communication efforts by project partners and social media will always be redirected to the CATCO2NVERS website. Traffic to the website will be increased by creating mutual links between the partners' websites and other relevant websites.

The project website contains:

- Latest news about the project progress and results
- Details about the project partners
- Informative materials (newsletter, infographics, articles)
- Contact information
- Social media links
- At least two videos (embedded from Youtube). The first one will explain the main objectives and scope of the project. The last one will serve as training material for stakeholders and will be produced by the end of the project.
- Privacy policy, cookies policy, and legal terms to comply with general data protection regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) on the protection of natural persons about the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

The project website is set up by SIE and will be managed, maintained, and hosted for the duration of the project and a further 2 years after the completion of the project. Statistical data will be collected about the website visitors that subsequently will be analysed by Google Analytics software and included in the project reports. The website will be responsive to work on a variety of devices and screen sizes, such as smartphones.

6.3 Content management system

For internal dissemination purposes, consortium partners will have access to a password-protected site (SharePoint established by the coordination, FUNDITEC) which will contain the proposal, consortium agreement, grant agreement, budget, deliverables, periodic reports, meeting, and workshop reports, and other relevant documents. Regular updates on the progress of the project will allow both internal monitoring of the project as well as rapid dissemination of the achievements.

6.4 Social media

The project has social media presence on Twitter (<https://twitter.com/Catco2N>), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/catco2nvers>) and Youtube (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/Catco2nvers>) to ensure wider dissemination to different age groups and target audiences. Social media will be used as a tool to announce project developments, but most importantly drive traffic to the project website.

Twitter, LinkedIn, and Youtube accounts have been established and content related to CATCO2NVERS has been posted regularly beginning M1 to increase outreach.

For the first phase of the project, the social media accounts will share posts related to the project scope and post on events where CATCO2NVERS is to be presented to build a community of interest, creating an audience for when there are project results to share.

Online media platforms will be monitored to provide information on the analytics, sources, types of content, and individuals/organisations that promote or disseminate project messages, allowing optimisation and targeting of communication to ensure maximum outreach of news or results. These results will also be included in interim reports and the final dissemination report. The social media accounts will be managed by SIE with support from the partners.

Consortium partners will follow the project's social media channels and engage with them as much as possible. Whenever possible, the partners will share posts on their corporate websites and social media networks. If they need assistance, SIE can guide them on the best ways to do so.

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6.5 Printed materials

A poster, a factsheet, a roll-up, and a brochure have been developed for distribution to partner networks and at conferences, exhibitions, and other events. The first project poster and brochure version contain general information about the research activities, participants, and expected results. In addition, a general PowerPoint presentation has also been created, presenting the project's objectives, methodology, partners, etc.

Image 6.5.1: CATCO₂NVERS poster (left) and factsheet (right)

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Image 6.5.2: CATCO₂NVERS brochure

PROJECT PARTNERS

FUNDITEC

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE

CARTIF

CSIC

persea biotechnology

avantium

Dan*no artificial nature

HYSTECH

noVA

AVA BIOCHEM

Sustainable INNOVATIONS

alchemia nova

EVYAP

JM Johnson Matthey Inspiring science, enhancing life

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www.catco2nvers.eu

@Catco2N

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CATCO₂NVERS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101000580.

DESCRIPTION

The overall idea of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the Bio-Based Industries transforming waste-CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 5 added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME), cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAMES) and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry, the project will process bio-based products replacing fossil material with a zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

IMPACTS

CATCO₂NVERS will advance in setting up sound business models which involve all the actors across the proposed value chains and consider the different scenarios of the technology implementation while bringing down environmental impacts and production costs

- Development of breakthrough technologies for the conversion of CO₂ into high added-value chemicals. Definition of processes targets including energy requirements, production costs, and yields
- Design of an integrated process with zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions
- New business models and value chains in the CO₂ utilisation sector.
- Diversification of the economic base of bio-based industries by 2030

METHODOLOGY

W1: CO₂ analysis and up-grading
Leader: DAN*NO; Tring: M1-16

W2: Electrocatalytic conversion of CO₂ to glyoxylic acid
Leader: AVANTIUM; Tring: M1-20

W3: Biocatalytic conversion of CO₂ to lactic acid
Leader: WAGENINGEN; Tring: M1-19

W4: Thermocatalytic conversion of CO₂ to platform chemicals (FDME, CCFAMES and Methanol)
Leader: FUNDITEC; Tring: M1-30

W5: Validation of technologies and added-value chemicals
Leader: FUNDITEC; Tring: M15-46

W6: Sustainability and circularity assessments
Leader: NOVA; Tring: M15-48

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions. To this end, the vision of the project revolves around two main axes:

- 1). Developing and applying catalyst-based technologies for CO₂ conversion to added-value chemicals
- 2). Validating technologies of TRL5 with industrial synthetic off-gases and providing sustainability and proofing socioeconomic and industrial feasibility.

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Image 6.5.3: CATCO₂NVERS Roll-up

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Image 6.5.4: CATCO₂NVERS PowerPoint

6.6 Newsletter and press releases

Electronic newsletters will be prepared every 6 months and will include project updates, announcements, interviews, and other information related to CATCO₂NVERS, to be distributed to stakeholders and partner networks and posted on the project website. Moreover, project updates may appear in partners' respective newsletters, which are distributed electronically to their contacts within their specific industry.

Press releases will be published to announce newsworthy developments during the project. They will be written in English and sent to the European press and national journalists, with the help of the project partners.

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Image 6.6: CATCO₂NVERS Press release

CATCO₂NVERS, a project that seeks to reduce greenhouse gas from the bio-based industries, kicks off

- CATCO₂NVERS is led by FUNDITEC and formed by fifteen partners from eight countries.
- CATCO₂NVERS has received €6,6 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

Madrid (Spain), May 27th, 2021. A European consortium is working on the implementation of CATCO₂NVERS, a new Horizon 2020 research and innovation project that kicked off this month and which aims to create added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions using integrated catalytic technologies.

The consortium is formed by fifteen partners from eight European countries that will work for 48 months to bring the use of CO₂ for the production of chemicals a step closer to industrial implementation taking into account their market projection and public perception to support the European Union in becoming a global leader in CO₂ re-use technologies.

The core purpose of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from the biobased industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes (electrochemical, enzymatic, and thermochemical). **The project objective is to transform waste-CO₂ from two biobased industries into five added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furan dicarboxylic methyl ester, cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters, and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics, and plastic industries.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000580.

6.7 Scientific journals and trade magazines

At least eight scientific papers will be prepared by the technical and academic partners. The project's results will be published in international scientific journals and trade magazines, such as the Journal of CO₂ Utilization, Journal of the American Chemical Society, Journal of the American Chemical Society, ChemSusChem, Journal of Power Sources, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, Energy and Fuels, Waste and Biomass Valorization, Green chemistry, Advanced materials, Journal of separation and purification technology, Biomass and Bioenergy and Catalysis today

6.8 Participation at conferences, workshops, and events

Project partners will attend sector-related events, conferences, workshops, to meet target groups, other stakeholders, public authorities, and the scientific community and to raise awareness about the project objectives and results. These events provide access to target audiences at local, national, European, and international levels.

Conferences and trade fairs of interest identified for the CATCO₂NVERS project are as follows:

Table 6.9: List of events and conferences identified

EVENT	DAY	LOCATION	LINK
2nd Carbon Dioxide Conversion Catalysis	November 8-9 2021	Online	https://www.rsc.org/events/detail/47592/2nd-carbon-dioxide-conversion-catalysis-virtual-conference
11th International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Applications	November 20-21, 2021	Zurich	https://iccsea2021.org/
European Blockchain Convention	December 13-16, 2021	Online	https://eblockchainconvention.com/
Global Experts conference on Materials Science & Nanotechnology 2021	December 2-4, 2021	Amsterdam	https://www.mscholarconferences.com/GECMN21/6/home.html#organizers
International Conference on Cellulose Fibres	February 2-3, 2022	Cologne	https://cellulose-fibres.eu/
JEC World	March 8-10, 2022	Paris	https://www.jec-world.events/
Biofuel Intl. Conference & Expo	March 15-16, 2022	Brussels	https://biofuels-news.com/conference/biofuels/biofuels_index_2022.php
EUBCE: The Leading Platform for Global Biomass Innovation	May 9-13, 2022	Florence	https://www.eubce.com/
The Renewable Materials Conference	May 10-12, 2022	Cologne	https://renewable-materials.eu/

International Symposium on Relations between Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Catalysis	June 26-29, 2022	Oslo	https://www.mn.uio.no/ishhc19
Renewable, resources and biorefineries	June 8-10, 2022	Ghent	https://rbconference.com/news/
XXII International Symposium on Homogeneous Catalysis	July 24-29, 2022	Lisbon	https://xxii-ishc.events.chemistry.pt/
Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference 2022	October 25-27, 2022	Espoo	https://ispt.eu/events/nordic-wood-biorefinery-conference/ https://www.vttresearch.com/en/news-and-ideas/nordic-wood-biorefinery-conference-2022
ECOMONDO	November 8-11, 2022	Rimini	https://www.showsbee.com/fairs/77889-Ecomondo-Rimini-2022.html

At the end of the project, a final conference will be organised where the partners will present the project results and perspectives to relevant stakeholders from the industry, the scientific community, regulatory bodies, and others with an interest in the field. The presentations will analyse and reflect upon the developments of CATCO2NVERS. Industry events are also contemplated to spread knowledge on the project upbringings.

7 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The social media activities will start as the project kicks off while the website waits to be activated. The publications and conferences presentations will take place as the project progresses and be published in the relevant locations on the website.

Publications and conference presentations are subject to project IP policy. Dissemination activities can be delayed as securing the business interests of any partner needs to be considered first.

The developed dissemination strategy will be continuously updated to ensure the maximum measurable project impact is achieved and the project website will be the central tool to track the progressive efficacy of the communication efforts.

Ambitious CATCO2NVERS indicators have been established :

Table 7.1: Indicators and targets

CATCO2NVERS

Tool/ Channel	Indicator	Target Number	Information Source
Brochure Leaflet Poster, Roll Up	N° of copies distributed	Material distribution: <300 poor; 300-500 good; >500 excellent	Consortium information, number of copies distributed to target groups / stakeholders
Project Website	Number of visits	Visits per year: <600 poor; 600 – 1,200 good; >1,200 excellent	Website statistics
Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Number of followers Number of impressions Engagement rate	Twitter; (a) Followers: < 50 poor; 50 – 100 good; > 150 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <0.2% poor; 0.2% - 0.9% good; > 0.9% excellent LinkedIn; (a) Followers: <50 poor; 50 – 100 good; >150 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <2% poor; 2- 3% good; >3% excellent	Social media analytics
Videos	Number of views	At least 2 in the project. Views: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent	Website / YouTube Analytics
Newsletter	Subscriber & Readers	1500 views (500 subscribers x 3 Newsletter)	Recording of e-mail sent, website download, analytics
Press Releases	Number of media stakeholders addressed Number of views on the website and social media	25 Media stakeholder; 1000 views per Press Release	Recording of e-mails sent, Media list, consulting media website
Scientific Publications	Number of Publications	8 scientific papers	Consulting site where publication is placed Contemplate ResearchGate as a platform
CATCO2NVERS Workshops	Number of attendees	3 EU workshop (M24, M30 & M36) 100 attendees	Registration list

CATCO2NVERS Webinars		2 Webinars x 10 participants (from M30)	Registration List
Conferences	Number of conferences attended	12 Conferences 1800 participants (12 conferences x 150 participants)	Registration List
Trade Fairs	Number of trade fairs attended	6 trade fairs 30000 participants (6 trade fair x 5000 participants)	Certificate of participation; Proof of registration; Event information, Business Trade fairs Cards exchanged

8 Levels of dissemination

Key targets groups operate at different geographic levels, which will influence which communication tools and media will be employed.

8.1 European level – EC

The European Commission will be informed about the results via the periodic reporting of the project (mid-term review, minutes of periodical meetings, updates of this document) in order to modify related regulations if necessary and to propose collaboration with other ongoing projects on dissemination activities.

8.2 International level – Industry, scientific community

The relevant international organisations will be informed of the results. Scientific knowledge can be translated into practical information, guidelines, and regulatory policies.

Direct mailing to specific organisations and stakeholders will be used to distribute electronic resources to raise public awareness.

Technical journals, conferences and workshops at both national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be used for the dissemination of knowledge both at research and industrial levels.

9 Methodology

CATCO₂NVERS

The following internal and external communication activities will be undertaken during the project's lifetime and afterward to ensure that the results of CATCO₂NVERS are efficiently and effectively communicated to the project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

9.1 Internal communication

Effective internal communication is key to sharing information and ensuring that the deliverables are met. Therefore, regular face-to-face meetings and conference calls will take place to exchange project information, update progress, and share results. Consortium and technical meetings will take place two times a year, while Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing services will be used to facilitate collaboration within WPs.

Apart from specific emails, taking advantage of the at least 6-monthly meetings, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination Plan and streamline a content curation process. This will allow the partners to take a more focused and systematic approach, strengthening actions taken to communicate and report on the project. A delegate from all consortium partners of CATCO₂NVERS will attend this meeting.

To facilitate efficient communication among partners, SIE will create a section within the website that will link to the project documentation and data exchange SharePoint created by the project coordinator FUNDITEC. This platform will host project materials for internal use, including regular updates on the project development, a project calendar, meeting documents (agendas, minutes, and presentations), manuscripts in progress, and project reports. The platform will have a content management system, allowing all partners to upload content themselves.

9.2 External communication

Every effort will be made to publicize the work of the consortium via the media, publications, conference presentations, trade fairs, and workshops, as well as through the Commission and industry bodies. Results of the project will be disseminated via reports, scientific papers, and technical articles. All public communication, and in particular scientific publications, will be made open access, to facilitate scientific exchange.

All project partners are expected to support dissemination, to ensure that stakeholders will be engaged throughout the lifetime of the project. Partners' activities may include but are not limited to: engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based), contributing to SIE's inputs on social media, proactively sharing information with SIE about project results, listing their communication activities in a

shared file, and providing SIE with translations of lay materials in their local language. Where possible, partners will translate press releases into their national languages and keep SIE informed about plans, by creating lists of national media channels they will try to reach.

10 Timeline

As the project has different development phases, the communication focus would be different across each of them.

10.1 Phase I: Awareness phase

The first phase of the project is the Pre-Development phase. It will take place during the first year of the project, from M1 to M12. No results have been generated yet, so the main communication activities will focus on raising awareness about the project, its objectives, and expected impacts. This will be done by making use of the project identity developed that includes the project logo and graphical visual identity; promoting the project website among stakeholders, and distributing communication and dissemination material such as the project's brochure. It is also key to identify the relevant stakeholders for CATCO2NVERS as well as to establish contact with similar initiatives. In this phase, the consortium partners will also participate in relevant events and conferences, will build strong networking relationships, and will contribute as well to the communication actions.

10.2 Phase II: Knowledge transfer

The second phase (M12-M36) aims to provide the different stakeholders with the first results of the project and to raise interest in the upcycling capacity of products and materials. The first workshops, webinars, and technical papers will start to be produced.

10.3 Phase III: Replication and exploitation

The third phase (M36-M42) consists of supporting the replication and exploitation actions of CATCO2NVERS. With the project coming to an end, it will be essential to link the exploitation and dissemination activities to guarantee the future replication of results. The final event will be celebrated openly during this period and all the knowledge and materials gathered in the project life will be made available online.

11 Actions M1-M6

11.1 Project identity and materials

In the first phase of the project, a visual identity for CATCO₂NVERS was created. It included the logo of the project, and the brand guidelines (typography, colours, iconography, photography style). Different communication materials were also developed, including a brochure, a roll-up, a poster, and a project presentation. A template for the deliverables, a word document template, and a PowerPoint template was produced and shared with the partners.

The first brochure, poster, factsheet, roll-up, and project presentation were produced and made available on the website of the project as soon as it was operative: <https://catco2nvers.eu/documents/>

Image 11.1.1: CATCO₂NVERS Word Template

Title 1

1 Title 2

1.1 Title 3

1.1.1 Subtitle 1

1.1.1.1 Subtitle 2

Text: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

11.2 Press Releases

A press release was launched at the beginning of the project. It was sent to approximately 200 local and trade media by SIE and several consortium partners.

It was published in more than 10 different media outlets, including Cordis, the partner's websites and social media, and trade media. Likewise, it was also uploaded to the CATCO2NVERS website.

Table 11.2.1: Media and partners publications

Media	Link
RETEMA	https://www.retema.es/noticia/catco2nvers-un-proyecto-que-busca-reducir-los-gei-de-las-industrias-de-base-biologica-Zl05m
CORDIS	https://cordis.europa.eu/article/rcn/430167_en.html
InterEmpresas	https://www.interempresas.net/Plastico/Articulos/352727-Dan-na-pone-marcha-planta-piloto-produccion-bioplasticos-sector-biomedico-tecno.html
Parc Científic de Barcelona	https://www.pcb.ub.edu/en/danna-pone-en-marcha-una-planta-piloto-de-produccion-de-biomateriales-en-el-pcb/
Partner	Link
FUNDITEC	https://funditec.es/funditec-suma-4-nuevos-proyectos-europeos-ademas-de-ser-responsable-de-la-coordinacion-de-uno-de-ellos/
SIE	https://sustainableinnovations.eu/catco2nvers-project-reduce-greenhouse-gas-co2/
AVT	https://www.avantium.com/press-releases/avantium-awarded-e178-million-in-total-from-eu-grants-for-the-development-of-electrochemical-processes-and-co2-based-polymers/
CARTIF	https://www.cartif.es/en/catco2nvers-en/
CARTIF	https://www.cartif.es/en/catco2nvers-reduce-greenhouse-gases-biobased-industries/
CARTIF + FUNDITEC	https://atlastecnologico.com/hacia-la-economia-circular-de-la-mano-de-los-centros-tecnologicos-siete-iniciativas-transformadoras/

CATCO2NVERS

ALC	https://www.alchemia-nova.net/projects/catco2nvers/
WR	https://research.wur.nl/en/projects/eu-21025-catco2nvers-creating-added-value-chemicals-from-bio-indu
HYSYTECH	https://www.hysytech.com/News/catco2nvers-kom-eng
EMI	https://www.emi-twente.nl/emi-twente-is-proud-to-participate-in-catco2nvers/

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 11.2: Example of publication

The screenshot shows a Cordis search results page for the project CATCO₂NVERS. The page header includes the European Commission logo, the Cordis search bar, and navigation links. The main content area features a news article titled "CATCO₂NVERS, a project that seeks to reduce greenhouse gas from the bio-based industries, kicks off". The article text states that the project is led by FUNDITEC and funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program. A contributor box on the right identifies the project as part of Sustainable Innovations Europe (SIAE) 2, led by MAGGI in Spain. Below the article is a large image of the CATCO₂NVERS logo over a cityscape. To the right, a "Related projects" section highlights the project's focus on creating added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions. At the bottom, there are social sharing options, a download button for the XML and PDF versions, and a "Booklet" icon.

European Commission
CORDIS
EU research results

English

HOME RESEARCH NEWS BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES NEWS & MEDIA PROJECTS & RESULTS ABOUT US

News

CATCO₂NVERS, a project that seeks to reduce greenhouse gas from the bio-based industries, kicks off

CATCO₂NVERS is led by FUNDITEC and formed by fifteen partners from eight countries. CATCO₂NVERS has received €6.6 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

NEW PRODUCTS AND TECHNOLOGIES

Contributor

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See more articles from this contributor

Related projects

HORIZON 2020

PROJECT

CATCO₂NVERS
Creating added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions using integrated catalytic technologies

10 September 2021

Madrid (Spain), May 27th, 2021. A European consortium is working on the implementation of CATCO₂NVERS, a new Horizon 2020 research and innovation project that kicked off this month and which aims to create added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions using integrated catalytic technologies.

The consortium is formed by fifteen partners from eight European countries that will work for 48 months to bring the use of CO₂ for the production of chemicals a step closer to industrial implementation taking into account their market potential and public perception to support the European Union in becoming a global leader in CO₂ re-use technologies.

The core purpose of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from the bio-based industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes (electrochemical, enzymatic, and thermochemical). The project objective is to transform waste-CO₂ from two bio-based industries into five added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furic dicarboxylic methyl ester, cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl ester, and bio-ethanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetic, and plastic industries.

CATCO₂NVERS will process bio-based products replacing fossil material with zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions, which will contribute to setting up sound business models involving all the value chain stakeholders and bringing down environmental impacts and production costs.

In summary, CATCO₂NVERS is focused on reducing industrial CO₂ emissions while exploring new procedures to produce bioproducts. With this aim, a bottom-up approach is used by the design and development of innovative catalytic technologies for the valorisation of CO₂ in the fabrication of different bio-based products, including monomers for bioplastics production, using CO₂ streams from biorefineries.

About CATCO₂NVERS

Coordinated by Foundation for Development and Technological Innovation (FUNDITEC), CATCO₂NVERS is formed by Aicheira-rock, Avantium Chemicals B.V., DAN'NA Artificial Nature, CARTIF, CSIC, EVYAR University of Twente, AXA Biochem, Hysitech, Nova-Institute, Johnson Matthey, PERGO Biotechnology, Stichting Wageningen Research, and Sustainable Innovations.

The project has received €6.6 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101000580.

Share this page

Download

XML PDF

Last update: 30 June 2021
Record number: 4301407

Booklet My Booklet

CATCO₂NVERS

11.3 Conferences attended

The CATCO₂NVERS consortium partners were encouraged to participate actively in the communication and dissemination actions and, as part of that, attendance at events, conferences, and shows is one of the main activities of the strategy. However, due to COVID-19 restrictions the participation in conferences and events has been low. Nevertheless, a list of upcoming events has been identified as displayed in Table 6.9 where partners will be encouraged to participate.

CATCO₂NVERS has been showcased in the PTECO₂ conference where the project coordinator spoke about the project to internal and external audiences.

The session was recorded and uploaded to CATCO₂NVERS's YouTube account and also to the website.

11.4 Social Media

The social media accounts on Twitter <https://twitter.com/Catco2N> LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/catco2nvers/> and Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/CATCO2NVERS> were set up at the beginning of the project and inaugurated with content on the kick-off meeting.

During this period, we shared 21 publications, achieved 78 followers, and our publications reached a total of 14,9K impressions on Twitter, as of October 13.

Image 11.4.1: Twitter Account

CATCO₂NVERS

We began the activity on LinkedIn on August 31st, 2021. In this period, and until September 30th, we have published 21 posts and achieved 140 followers. The publications reached more than 13.500 impressions.

Image 11.4.2: LinkedIn Account

Additionally, a video has been uploaded to CATCO2NVERS's YouTube channel

Image 11.4.3: YouTube channel

CATCO₂NVERS

11.5 Newsletter

The first newsletter of CATCO₂NVERS' project was released on September 28 and published on the [website](#)

Image 11.5.1: Newsletter 1

NEWSLETTER 1 | SEPTEMBER 2021

CATCO₂NVERS, A PROJECT THAT SEEKS TO REDUCE GREENHOUSE GAS FROM THE BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES, KICKS OFF

Transforming waste-CO₂ into 5 added-value chemicals with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry

CATCO₂NVERS consortium members were reunited to present the future work each one is going to develop to achieve the goals of the project.

During the teleconference, hosted by [FUNDITEC](#), the partners were able to explain their future responsibilities within the project, as well as to show their corporate presentations.

The core purpose of CATCO₂NVERS is to **reduce greenhouse gas emissions** (GHG) from the biobased industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes.

The consortium is formed by **fifteen partners** from eight European countries that will work for 48 months to bring the use of CO₂ for the production of chemicals a step closer to industrial implementation

[READ MORE](#)

HAVE YOU ALREADY SEEN THE CATCO₂NVERS MATERIALS?

We have prepared a set of **dissemination materials** to raise the awareness about our project objectives and goals. Download them by clicking below

[DOWNLOAD NOW](#)

CATCO₂NVERS AT THE PTECO₂ TECHNICAL WEBINAR

On June 22, the [Spanish CO₂ Technology Platform](#) (PTECO₂) counted on the presence of CATCO₂NVERS project. There, [Dulce Muñoz](#), Scientific & Technical Manager from [FUNDITEC](#), showcased CATCO₂NVERS, on behalf of the consortium, the project scope, and approach under the topic of **catalytic conversion of CO₂ into chemical intermediates of industrial value**.

PTECO₂ webinar was held virtually in Spanish language in collaboration with [AEI](#) and [INCAB-CSIC](#). The session was structured in several lectures delivered by recognised speakers, both from academia and industry, in the framework of the **potential uses and transformations of CO₂ in Spain**.

[WATCH NOW](#)

CATCO₂NVERS IMPACTS & METHODOLOGY

Development of breakthrough technologies for the conversion of CO₂ into high added-value chemicals. Definition of processes targets including energy requirements, production costs, and yields.

Design of an integrated process with zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

New business models and value chains in the CO₂ utilisation sector.

Diversification of the economic base of bio-based industries by 2030.

CATCO₂NVERS PARTNERS

Coordinated by Foundation for Development and Technological Innovation (FUNDITEC), CATCO₂NVERS is formed by Alchemia-nova, AVA Biochem, Avantium Chemicals BV, CARTIF, CSIC, DAN*NA Artificial Nature, EVYAP, University of Twente, Hysytech, Nova-Institute, Johnson Matthey, PERSEO Biotechnology, Sustainable Innovations and Wageningen Food & Biobased Research.

[VISIT OUR WEBSITE AND FOLLOW ON SOCIAL MEDIA!](#)

We will be posting all the project developments, actions and news on our website and social media channels. Follow us to make sure you do not miss anything out!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000580

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You can update your preferences or unsubscribe from this list

Grow your business with mailchimp

CATCO₂NVERS

11.6 Website

The website <https://catco2nvers.eu/> was launched on June 25th (M2) with essential information of the project that will be updated constantly with progress and news from the project and partners.

Image 11.6.1: CATCO₂NVERS website

CATCO₂NVERS
Creating added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions using integrated catalytic technologies.
[READ MORE](#)

WHAT IS CATCO₂NVERS?

The overall idea of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the bio-based industries transforming waste CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 3 added-value chemicals: glycolic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME), cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAME) and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry, the project will produce bio-based products replacing fossil material with a zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

[DISCOVER THE PARTNERS](#)

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions. To this end, the vision of the project revolves around two main axes:

- Developing and applying catalyst-based technologies for CO₂ conversion to added-value chemicals
- Validating technologies at TRL5 with industrial synthetic off-gases and providing sustainability and proving socioeconomic and industrial feasibility.

NEWS

- Interview with University of Twente**
"We will be able to demonstrate that it is possible to use captured CO₂ to produce..."
- Interview with NOVA-Institut**
"Our goal is to support a process development that leads to products and processes which cause..."
- Are you already subscribed to our newsletter?**
The CATCO₂NVERS project

11.6.1 Website analytics

Since the website has been operative until 12/10/2021, it has accounted for 2370 visits and the average time that a user spends on it is 5:38 minutes. These numbers are very good and indicate that the project is getting very qualified website traffic.

Figure 11.6.1: Web analytics. Source: Google Analytics

Figure 11.6.2: Website top locals

12 Actions M7-M18

This section corresponds to the update of the Communication & Dissemination Plan D7.2 (M6) led by SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS (SIE). Throughout this section, a complete description of the activities carried out during the month 7 (M7) to month 18 (M18) period in terms of Communication and Dissemination will be further explained.

Likewise, the Communication and Dissemination strategy for the upcoming period will be included. All partners contributed to dissemination and communication activities in line with the aims and goals of the plan.

12.1 Project identity and materials

At the beginning of the project, CATCO₂NVERS produced a series of printed documents (brochure, poster, factsheet, and roll-up) to be distributed at the events attended by partners.

As the COVID-19 restrictions have been lifted SIE handled during the first face-to-face General Assembly meeting a set of 30 brochures per partner. A total of 450 brochures were distributed to the partners in order to disseminate the project when participating in events, trade fairs or conferences.

Image 12.1.1: Printed materials in the General Assembly Meeting

From its side, SIE handled FUNDITEC the official roll-up of the project as the coordination organised in M15 a conference about catalytic solutions for a sustainable industry. In addition to this event, FUNDITEC also used the printed materials in other events such as the 20th International Zeolite Conference.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 12.1.2: Marcelo Echeverri (researcher at FUNDITEC) at the 20th International Zeolite Conference in a poster presentation holding a set of CATCO₂NVERS brochures

For their part, NOVA also handled several brochures at the Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels and Chemicals:

Image 12.1.3: Matthias Stratmann (Head of Sustainability at NOVA) at the Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels and Chemicals

Furthermore, partners are encouraged to share with stakeholders the online versions, made available on the website of the roll-up, brochure, factsheet, project presentation and poster.

12.2 Conferences attended

As mentioned in the 12.7 section, due to some of the suspensions of the COVID-19 restrictions, the CATCO2NVERS consortium has been able to attend more than ten conferences, events and trade fairs in the framework of a wide variety of areas such as cosmetic, pharma sector, R&D, plastic sector, among others:

- [SusPlast Event](#) – October 2021, CSIC. Keynote lecture
- [InnoFUTURO Conference](#) – November 2021, PERSEO. Keynote Lecture
- [X CM-10 Macromolecules Colloquium](#) – December 2021, CSIC. Online presentation.
- [International Seminar Biotechnology Applied to the Plastic Sector](#) – March 2022, PERSEO. Poster presentation.
- [Conference on Co2-Based Fuels and Chemicals](#) – March 2022, NOVA. Stakeholders engagement.
- [11th Conference of the framework program for research and innovation of the European Union, "The New Horizon for Europe"](#) – April 2022, FUNDITEC. Poster presentation.
- [Cosmofarma Exhibition](#) – May 2022, EVYAP. Stakeholders engagement.
- [GEPSAL 2022 Conference, Europe Day and Event in the Materials Physics Center](#) – May 2022, CSIC. Keynote lecture.
- [International Trade Fair Cosmetic Business 2022](#) – June 2022, EVYAP. Stakeholders engagement.
- [17th International Cosmetics, Beauty, Hair Exhibition: Beautyeurasia](#) – June 2022, EVYAP. Stakeholders engagement.
- [20th International Zeolite Conference](#) – July 2022, FUNDITEC. Poster presentation.

12.3 Events organised

Following the phases described in the [Timeline section](#) of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, no events were foreseen during the awareness phase (M1-M12) of the project. As M18, the project is now in the knowledge transfer phase where the first workshops, webinars, and technical papers will start to be produced. For their part, FUNDITEC organised a conference in the framework of [catalytic solutions for a sustainable industry](#). The session was celebrated in collaboration with JM, CSIC who

CATCO₂NVERS

introduced also some of the sister initiatives of CATCO₂NVERS: [FRACTION](#) and [CO₂SMOS](#).

12.4 Interaction with EU projects

Clustering, with other EU-related initiatives, is also an important part of the communication and dissemination of the project. SIE started to reach some of these initiatives in M9 and successfully could organise an [internal call](#) in M10 to start seeking new synergies and potential collaborations. The call was led by SIE. The CATCO₂NVERS project engaged with the [CO₂SMOS](#) and [VIVALDI](#) projects which are under the same European topic "Bio-based industries leading the way in turning carbon dioxide emissions into chemicals".

Image 12.4.1: The CATCO₂NVERS Project explores new related projects to collaborate with under the bio-based industries leading the way in turning carbon dioxide emissions into chemicals topic

During the session, the CO₂SMOS project explained its role to transform the carbon emissions generated from bioprocesses into different sustainable bioproducts; VIVALDI showcased its approach how to converting off-gas emissions from bio-based Industries into CO₂-based chemicals; for their part, the CATCO₂NVERS project presented the concept to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the Bio-Based Industries transforming waste-CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 5 added-value chemicals.

12.5 Social Media

The social media channels were put in place at the beginning of the project. In the following section, a description of the performance is conducted in terms of number of followers, number of posts, engagement rate levels as well as graphics and analytics.

12.5.1 LinkedIn

CATCO₂NVERS's presence on LinkedIn has reached 285 followers by M18 after 56 updates. The engagement rate in this platform (number of interactions with post-likes, comments, shares) has reached 5,20% (more than 2% is considered excellent performance).

The number of impressions (views) from M6 to M18 is around 30000.

Image 12.5.1.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS LinkedIn profile. This data does not reflect the October analytics)

Metrics

12.5.2 Twitter

As of October 2022, CATCO₂NVERS has 210 followers on this social media channel after 56 updates. The content on the profile has generated more than 18000 views from M6 to M18. The current engagement rate for Twitter is 3,12% (higher than 0,5% is considered great performance).

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M7-M9

Your Tweets earned **6.6K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M10-M12

Your Tweets earned **6.4K impressions** over this **89 day period**

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M13-M15

Your Tweets earned **2.7K impressions** over this **89 day period**

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M16-M18 (Data of this quarter is not entirely reflected)

Your Tweets earned **2.4K impressions** over this **59 day** period

12.5.3 YouTube

At least two videos were expected to be produced along with the project's lifetime. To date, CATCO₂NVERS has uploaded two videos reaching more than 200 views in total. The official video of the project was uploaded in M9. SIE will upload the audio-visual content when generating (recordings of workshops, posters presentations, etc.)

Image 12.5.3.1: CATCO₂NVERS videos on YouTube

12.6 Newsletters

As mentioned in the Grant Agreement, it is expected that eight newsletters would be released during the project life. The first newsletter (M5) included the main information of the project such as the methodology, impacts, and partners as well as the first press release and the communication materials. CATCO₂NVERS's second newsletter (M11)

CATCO₂NVERS

contained information about the first general assembly meeting, information on the new collaboration with the related projects CO2SMOS and VIVALDI, events attended, the official project video, and partners interviews.

The third newsletter (M17) contained the relevant actions carried out in the last semester of the project such as the upcoming general assembly plus the second general assembly meeting, the two technical milestones achieved, all the conferences and events attended as well as two more partners interviews.

As of M18, the Newsletter has 107 subscribers and an average of 40 readers per Newsletter. The Newsletters are also uploaded to the Documents section on the CATCO₂NVERS website. From there, users can easily access each Newsletter and subscribe to receive upcoming ones.

Image 12.6.1: Documents Section: CATCO₂NVERS Newsletters

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 12.6.1: Newsletter 2 (left side) Newsletter 3 (right side).

NEWSLETTER 2 | MARCH 2022

CATCO₂NVERS HOLDS ITS FIRST GENERAL ASSEMBLY MEETING

GENERAL ASSEMBLY
NOVEMBER 5, 2021
CATCO₂NVERS

The CATCO₂NVERS project held its first **General Assembly** meeting on 5 November in a hybrid way where some partners could attend physically while others were connected via teleconference. The session was celebrated at **FUNDITEC'S** facilities in Madrid, Spain.

During the meeting, the consortium partners exposed the advancement of each work package as well as discussed the next actions for the upcoming semester

[READ MORE](#)

CATCO₂NVERS EXPLORES NEW SYNERGIES WITH VIVALDI AND CO₂SMOS PROJECTS

On February 3rd, 2022, the CATCO₂NVERS project held an online meeting together with the initiatives **CO₂SMOS** and **VIVALDI** to explore future collaborations under the framework of bio-based industries leading the way in turning carbon dioxide emissions

The core of the session was to introduce the **project's scope** and share some of the **best practices** to collaborate. With the strong competencies of the three projects, CATCO₂NVERS, CO₂SMOS, and VIVALDI will be able to boost the development of turning carbon

for Research & Innovation

NEWSLETTER 3 | SEPTEMBER 2022

CATCO₂NVERS WILL HOLD ITS THIRD GENERAL ASSEMBLY MEETING

CATCO₂NVERS, the progress after one year of running

On November 2022, the CATCO₂NVERS consortium partners will meet in Istanbul, Turkey to discuss the latest progress and advancements carried out in the last semester. Hosted by **DVYAP**, the partners will have the opportunity to establish synergies, collaborations as well as to define future actions for the next period. Have a look at the previous General Assembly meeting celebrated in the Netherlands.

[READ MORE](#)

CATCO₂NVERS ACHIEVES TWO MILESTONES

The **University of Twente** has created a report detailing the most reasonable routes for upgrading the CO₂ streams. It started with the reports delivered by our project partners, **Avantium** and **PERSEO**, who shared information about the composition of their CO₂-rich streams. With all that information, the University of Twente compared those compositions and established that the first was a typical post-combustion CO₂ stream, while the other was similar to that obtained from an oxy-combustion process.

The CATCO₂NVERS consortium has worked on the analysis of the compositions of the two gas streams at **PERSEO** and **Avantium** and the definition of the two synthetic gas compositions for demonstration of the technologies.

CARTIF has determined the trace element limits of industrial gas streams for the methanol production process. For this purpose, **CARTIF** has used the composition of the different gases provided by **PERSEO** and **Avantium** and has determined the possible undesired effects on the catalyst performance.

[READ MORE](#)

funding from the ECU0580. This document is the property of the European Union and neither the European Commission nor any member of the CATCO₂NVERS Consortium is liable for any use that may be made of the information

under university of Twente in the Netherlands

12.7 Website

Since the official release of the website on M2, CATCO₂NVERS partners have contributed widely to its update by providing information on milestones, giving interviews, consolidating dissemination materials, etc.

As a living platform, the website has evolved from M6 to M18 to include all the relevant actions, news, articles and relevant documents developed within the CATCO₂NVERS framework.

Regarding the News section, in the last semester 23 blog posts have been published:

- [Interview with Alchemia Nova](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS holds its first General Assembly Meeting](#)
- [Interview with AVANTIUM](#)
- [Interview with CSIC](#)
- [SusPlast Event](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS explores new related projects to collaborate](#)
- [InnoFUTURO Conference](#)
- [X CM-10 Macromolecules Colloquium](#)
- [International Seminar Biotechnology Applied to the Plastic Sector](#)
- [Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels and Chemicals](#)
- [11th Conference of the framework program for research and innovation of the European Union, "The New Horizon for Europe"](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS, the progress after one year of running](#)
- [Interview with CARTIF](#)
- [Cosmofarma Exhibition](#)
- [GEPSAL 2022 Conference, Europe Day and Event in the Materials Physics Center](#)
- [Catco2nvers achieves a new milestone: Theoretical Route for CO₂ Upgrading](#)
- [International Trade Fair Cosmetic Business 2022](#)

- [Catco2nvers achieves a new milestone: Analysis of the compositions of the two gas streams and definition of the two synthetic gas compositions](#)
- [FUNDITEC organises a conference about catalytic solutions for a sustainable industry](#)
- [17th International Cosmetics, Beauty, Hair Exhibition: Beautyeurasia](#)
- [20th International Zeolite Conference](#)
- [Interview with DAN*NA](#)

Likewise, during this period the following documents have been uploaded to the CATCO2NVERS website:

- [D7.1 Project Website](#)
- [D7.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)
- [Newsletter 1](#)
- [Newsletter 2](#)
- [Newsletter 3](#)

From M7 to M18 the CATCO2NVERS website has gained around 1000 unique visitors with an average session duration of 02:45 minutes which means that the audience is very engaged with the content of the website.

During the last month, SIE started to design a new tracking system to evaluate the performance of the website. Due to the new Google Analytics software and updates, the system used until now will be obsoleted to monitor the upcoming periods. For that reason, SIE will explore different routes through Google Analytics 4 (GA4).

12.8 Partners contribution

As stated in the Grant Agreement Article 29 “Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).”

In compliance with this article, our partners have actively contributed to disseminating the CATCO2NVERS project from the very beginning by different means: social media posts, attendance at conferences and shows, email campaigns, newsletters, press releases, etc. to good effect.

CATCO₂NVERS LinkedIn posts have been shared more than 100 times from M7-M18 and the partners were very supportive in this area. Likewise, consortium members have also made different posts during M7-M18 about CATCO₂NVERS plus reported the social media post from CATCO₂NVERS social media channels.

Some partners have accounts on other media channels and they have disseminated the project as well over there. The full partner's contribution is listed in the dissemination tables (Annex 1).

13 Actions M19-M30

This section corresponds to the update of the Communication & Dissemination Plan D7.2 (M6) led by SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS (SIE). Throughout this section, a complete description of the activities carried out during the month 19 (M19) to month 30 (M30) period in terms of Communication and Dissemination will be further explained.

Likewise, the Communication and Dissemination strategy for the upcoming period will be included. All partners contributed to dissemination and communication activities in line with the aims and goals of the plan.

13.1 Project identity and materials

During the period reported (M19-M30) the partners have distributed several communication materials produced by SIE at the beginning of the project such as the roll-up and brochures.

On June 6, 2023, our partner University of Twente organised an Open House event for young and old people curious about science and technology. Most of the communication materials were showcased during the activity including the project roll-up, brochures, and the official video among others.

Image 13.1.1: University of Twente Open House Event.

CATCO₂NVERS

Additionally, other scientific communication materials were produced by the technical partners such as poster presentations. In December 2023, Wageningen University & Research showcased CATCO₂NVERS during the NVBMB (The Dutch society for biochemistry and molecular biology) through a poster presentation where the concept, methodology, impact and objectives of the project were explained under the topic “The expanding world of biological one-carbon fixation – made by nature & engineers”.

Image 13.1.2: Daan van Vliet (WUR) in the NVBMB event

On May 11, 2023, our technical project coordinator Dulce Muñoz, researcher in FUNDITEC, introduced the CATCO₂NVERS project during the Spanish conference entitled “adding value to CO₂” organised by PTECO₂ and SUSCHEM ES in Bilbao, Spain. Additionally, Eva Maya from CSIC contributed to disseminating the CATCO₂NVERS project by presenting two posters with FUNDITEC.

Image 13.1.3: Dulce Muñoz (FUNDITEC) in the PTECO₂ event.

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CATCO₂NVERS

Finally, on March 1-2, 2023 our entity coordinator FUNDITEC attended again together with CSIC, the VIII International Seminar of Bioplastics and Sustainable Composites in Valencia, Spain where they showcased the initiative through a poster presentation in the framework of CO₂ thermocatalytic conversions that give rise to useful intermediates in biopolymers synthesis.

Image 13.1.4: Poster presented at the VIII International Seminar of Bioplastics and Sustainable Composites

Furthermore, partners have been encouraged again to share with stakeholders the online versions, made available on the website as well as sharing them on social media.

Image 13.1.4: Example of social media post sharing the CATCO₂NVERS poster.

CATCO₂NVERS

Last but not least, new communication materials have been designed in collaboration with the related projects CO₂SMOS and VIVALDI with the aim of explaining the importance of Europe leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals to a non-scientific audience.

Image 14.1.5: Example of social media post sharing the CATCO₂NVERS poster.

More information about the clustering can be found in the 13.4 section: Interaction with other EU projects.

13.2 Conferences attended

In the current period, the partners attended ten conferences and events to disseminate the CATCO₂NVERS project. Most of the events listed below have been properly disseminated on the project website as well as social media (hyperlinks are included):

- 15th European congress on catalysis. August 2023, CSIC. Keynote lecture.
- The Netherlands Process Technology Symposium, July 2023, EMI. Keynote lecture.
- International Congress on Membranes and Membrane Processes, July 2023 EMI. Keynote lecture.
- Biennial Meeting of the Spanish Catalysis Society, June 2023. Poster presentation.
- PTECO₂ Event. May, 2023. FUNDITEC and CSIC. Keynote lecture and poster presentation.

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- Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels & Chemicals. April 2023, FUNDITEC. Keynote lecture.
- Stakeholder dialogue on the circular economy: from research to implementation, April 2023, ALCHEMIA NOVA. Keynote lecture and stakeholders' engagement.
- VIII International Seminar Of Bioplastics And Sustainable Composites, March 2023, FUNDITEC, CSIC. Poster presentation.
- NVBMB Fall Meeting, December 2022, Wageningen. Poster presentation.
- 18th Aachener Membran Kolloquium, November 2022, EMI. Trade fair and stakeholder engagement.

Image 13.2: Example of website event creativities:

13.3 Events organised

As M18, the project is now in the knowledge transfer phase where the first workshops, webinars, and technical papers started to be produced.

SIE and EMI collaborated together to disseminate the project to a non-scientific audience taking the advance of the University Of Twente Open House 2023. The session included a wide variety of activities such as workshops, guided tours, quizzes, and demonstrations where children and young students were able to learn about the initiative. Children were also allowed to create their membranes, adding an

CATCO₂NVERS

interactive element to the event. Most of the communication materials were showcased during the activity including the project roll-up, brochures, and the official video among others.

Image 13.3.1: Images of the EMI Open House 2023.

In this context, our partner CSIC also organised an event in the framework of Schuman Declaration from May 8 to May 10, 2023 that brought together young students and researchers working within the European scientific community. The goal was to showcase the research conducted within the European framework and highlight the opportunities that the European Union provides for participation, promotion, and funding across diverse fields such as biology, materials science, chemistry, physics, and more. Beatriz Fuerte Diez, PhD student at CSIC, showcased the CATCO₂NVERS project among the general public, including young students and children. Its objectives and accomplishments were shared to raise awareness and understanding of the project's importance in tackling carbon dioxide conversion.

Image 13.3.2: Commemorating the Schuman Declaration. Event organised by CSIC.

CATCO2NVERS

Finally, as part of the interaction with other EU initiatives, SIE organised a joint webinar in collaboration with CO2SMOS and VIVALDI in the framework of Leading the way in turning CO2 emissions into chemicals where more than one hundred attendees enjoyed and learnt about the ambition, objectives, impacts, methodologies and concepts of each initiative showcased. The online webinar presented the different technologies and workflows in each project for turning CO2 into chemicals and it was opened to anyone who wanted to learn more about these initiatives and the different carbon capture methods and conversions.

Image 13.3.3: Screenshot during the webinar Leading the way in turning CO2 emissions into chemicals.

13.4 Interaction with EU projects

In the clustering meetings with CO2SMOS and VIVALDI reported during the M7 – M18, the three initiatives started to define joint activities to maximise impacts and engage with the different target audiences.

As explained in the previous section 13.1 Project identity and materials, one of the joint actions was to develop a joint handbook with an user-friendly design explaining the importance of Europe Leading the way in turning CO2 emissions into chemicals as well as the ambition behind the three related projects since all of them share a common topic. SIE develop the format, content, and layout of this document while COSMOS and VIVALDI introduced their project information.

CATCO₂NVERS

The first part of the handbook is focused on providing a clear explanation of the need to investigate carbon capture utilisation. In this context, the objectives and impact of the three projects are explained concerning this theme. The second part of the handbook aims not only to explain and define easily the concept, objectives and processes of the three initiatives but also to give a comprehensive definition of the keywords that difficult for a non-scientific audience to understand the whole project. For that purpose, a YES, BUT... approach was conducted creating a double page where the user can easily do a deeper look at the technical concepts such as *catalytic process*, *bio-based industry*, etc.

Image 13.4.1: Example of double page of the joint handbook.

2. The ambition of three European Solutions

2.1 CATCO₂NVERS

The overall idea of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the Bio-Based Industries transforming waste-CO₂ from 2 bio-based Industries into 5 added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME), cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAMEs) and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry, the project will process bio-based products replacing fossil material with a zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

OBJECTIVES

- Developing and applying catalyst-based technologies for CO₂ conversion to added-value chemicals.
- Validating technologies with industrial synthetic off-gases and providing sustainability and proving socioeconomic and industrial feasibility.

PROCESS

The core purpose of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the bio-based industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes (electrochemical, enzymatic, and thermochemical).

The project aim is to transform waste-CO₂ from two bio-based Industries into five added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furan dicarboxylic methyl ester, cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters, and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics, and plastic Industries.

YES, BUT....

What is a Bio-Based Industry?

A bio-based industry is a sector of the economy that uses living organisms or their derivatives to produce various goods and services. This can include industries that produce food, beverages, chemicals, fuels, and other products. Reusing CO₂ in the bio industry has the potential to provide numerous environmental, economic, and social benefits, making it an important area for continued research and development.

What is a catalytic process?

A catalytic process is a chemical reaction that is facilitated or accelerated by a substance called a catalyst. A catalyst works by lowering the activation energy required for a reaction to occur, allowing it to proceed at a faster rate or under milder conditions than would be possible without the catalyst. In other words, it is a chemical reaction that is made faster, more efficient, or more environmentally friendly by the presence of a catalyst.

Do I see those chemicals in my day to day?

- Glyoxylic acid (GA)** is used in the production of pharmaceuticals, dyes, resins, and other chemicals. It is also used as a reducing agent in the synthesis of a variety of organic compounds.
- Lactic acid (LA)** is used in the production of biodegradable plastics, as well as in the food industry as a flavoring agent and preservative. It is also used in the cosmetic and personal care industry as a pH adjuster.
- Furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME)** can be used to produce polymers, resins, and other materials with improved performance and sustainability compared to traditional petroleum-based products.
- Cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAMEs)** are used as starting materials for the production of bio-based chemicals and materials, such as surfactants, lubricants, and biodegradable plastics.
- Bio-methanol** is a renewable alternative to petroleum-based methanol. It is used as a fuel, solvent, and starting material for the production of chemicals, such as formaldehyde and acetic acid. Bio-methanol can also be converted into biofuels, such as bio-diesel and bio-jet fuel.

The three projects also agreed to create a joint social media strategy to share the handbook on their respective communication channels (Website, LinkedIn and Twitter) respecting the YES, BUT... approach.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 13.4.2: Example of social media post about the joint factsheet following the YES, BUT... approach

As of September 2023, the handbook has gained more than 1,000 impressions on social media (counting only the analytics of CATCO2NVERS).

Additionally, SIE organised a joint webinar with the same topic but aiming to reach a scientific target within the research, academia, and industry. On April 12, 2023, the three sister projects organised an [online joint webinar](#) where more than one hundred attendees enjoyed and learnt about the ambition, objectives, impacts, methodologies and concepts of each initiative showcased. The online webinar presented the different technologies and workflows in each project for turning CO₂ into chemicals and it was opened to anyone who wanted to learn more about these initiatives and the different carbon capture methods and conversions.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 13.4.3: Joint webinar agenda: The Importance of Europe Leading the Way in Turning CO₂ Emissions into Chemicals.

WEBINAR AGENDA	
11:00 – 11:10	1 WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION Pablo Morales Moya SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS
11:10 – 11:30	2 INTRODUCING CATCO₂NVERS Dulce Muñoz FUNDITEC
11:30 – 11:40	3 BREAK OUT SESSION Pablo Morales Moya SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS
11:40 – 12:00	4 INTRODUCING VIVALDI Albert Guisasaola UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA DE BARCELONA
12:00 – 12:20	5 INTRODUCING CO₂SMOS Raúl Piñero CARTIF
12:20 – 12:30	6 WRAP-UP, Q&A Lara Tottolo CO ₂ VALUE EUROPE Pablo Morales Moya SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS

CATCO₂NVERS vivaldi CO₂SMOS

Future conversations will be established to keep defining new communication strategies to maximise impacts and efforts in the upcoming periods.

13.5 Social Media

In the following section, a description of the performance is conducted in terms of the number of followers, number of posts, engagement rate levels as well as graphics and analytics.

13.5.1 LinkedIn

CATCO₂NVERS's presence on LinkedIn has reached 457 followers by M29 after 60 updates. The engagement rate in this platform (number of interactions with post-likes, comments, and shares) has reached 8,85% (more than 2% is considered excellent performance).

The number of impressions (views) from M19 to M29 is around 22500.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 13.5.1.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS LinkedIn profile. This data does not reflect the October analytics)

Metrics

13.5.2 Twitter

As of September 2023, CATCO₂NVERS has 283 followers on this social media channel after 60 updates. The content on the profile has generated more than 10,000 views from M19 to M29. The current engagement rate for Twitter is around 4% (higher than 0,5% is considered great performance).

Image 13.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M19-M21

Your Tweets earned **2.9K impressions** over this **90 day period**

Image 13.5.2.2: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M22-M24.

Your Tweets earned **3.1K impressions** over this **91 day** period

Image 13.5.2.3: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M25-M27

Your Tweets earned **3.5K impressions** over this **90 day** period

Image 13.5.2.4: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M28-M29 (Data of this time period is not entirely reflected as of September 11, 2023)

Your Tweets earned **999 impressions** over this **72 day** period

13.5.3 YouTube

To date, CATCO₂NVERS has uploaded six videos reaching more than 350 views in total. SIE has started a proactive campaign with the support of the technical partners involved in the development of the five conversion technologies. This campaign is scheduled to be released in the last quarter of the year. The main objective of this

CATCO₂NVERS

campaign is to explain how the leading technology partners are progressing and conducting their workflows to convert CO₂ into high-value-added chemicals. The campaign is entitled Five Co₂nversion Technologies:

- Technology one: From CO₂ to Lactic Acid.
- Technology two: From CO₂ to Glyoxylic Acid.
- Technology three: From CO₂ to Furan Dicarboxylic Methyl Ester.
- Technology four: From CO₂ to Cyclic Carbonates.
- Technology five: From CO₂ to Bio-Methanol.

Image 12.5.3.1: Five Co₂nversion Technologies intro.

The partners that are collaborating in this video campaign are the leaders of these technologies: Avantium, Wageningen University & Research, CARTIF, and FUNDITEC. Additionally, SIE has collaborated with Nova-Institute to produce one extra video about the importance of Life Cycle Assessment within the CATCO₂NVERS project which is already available on the project YouTube Channel: [About Life Cycle Assessment And Its Importance In The Catco2nvers Project.](#)

Last but not least, SIE has added subtitles in ten languages in the [CATCO₂NVERS official video](#) to make the video more comprehensive for all kinds of audiences. This video has been translated into the following languages: Catala, Dutch, English, French, German, Portuguese, Spanish, Turkish, and Ukrainian.

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13.6 Newsletters

As of M29, the Newsletter has 387 subscribers and an average of 60 readers per Newsletter. The Newsletters are also uploaded to the [Documents section](#) on the CATCO₂NVERS website. From there, users can easily access each Newsletter and subscribe to receive upcoming ones.

Image 13.6.1: Documents Section: CATCO₂NVERS Newsletters

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 13.6.1: Newsletter 4 (left side) Newsletter 5 (right side).

NEWSLETTER 4 | MARCH 2023

FREE ONLINE WEBINAR

LEADING THE WAY IN TURNING CO₂ EMISSIONS INTO CHEMICALS

The fight against **climate change** is an ongoing battle, and one of the biggest contributors to this problem is the **emission of CO₂** into the atmosphere. While CO₂ is a naturally occurring gas, the increase in human activities has led to a sharp rise in CO₂ levels, which is having a devastating effect on our planet. Thankfully, there are forward-thinking European projects that are **leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals**: CATCO₂NVERS, CO₂SMOS, and VIVALDI are innovative projects that are using cutting-edge technology to capture CO₂ emissions and turn them into **valuable chemicals**.

[REGISTER FOR FREE NOW](#)

CATCO₂NVERS HOLD ITS FIRST

REVIEW MEETING WITH THE RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY

On January 18, 2023, the CATCO₂NVERS consortium held the **Review Meeting with the Research Executive Agency** hosted by CEC (Spanish National Research Council) in Brussels.

The meeting was an opportunity to provide an introduction and overview of the CATCO₂NVERS project and its different work packages.

The **Research Executive Agency** followed up on the progress made by the CATCO₂NVERS project team and praised their efforts to address the challenges faced. The European Commission agency also provided valuable feedback and suggestions for future developments, which are being taken into consideration.

NEWSLETTER 5 | SEPTEMBER 2023

THE PROGRESS AFTER TWO YEARS OF RUNNING

On May 8th and 9th 2023, the partners of the CATCO₂NVERS project had the opportunity to meet and discuss the latest progress of this initiative that is seeking to create added-value chemicals by using the CO₂ of two bio-based industries. The meeting was organised by CARTIF in Valladolid, Spain.

On the first day, the consortium showcased the progress and some results of the technical work packages as well as the current status in the dissemination, communication and exploitation side.

On the second day, the meeting continued with a discussion of the upcoming milestones and deliverables for the project, with the partners agreeing on a clear plan of action for the next few months.

Finally, the consortium enjoyed a tour through the CARTIF facilities where they learned how they are working in the conversion of CO₂ to Bio-Methanol.

[READ MORE](#)

CLUSTERING WITH OUR SISTER PROJECTS

JOINT WORKSHOP WITH CO₂SMOS AND VIVALDI PROJECTS

On April 12, 2023, the three sister projects organised an online joint webinar in the framework of **Leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals** where more than one hundred of attendees enjoyed and learnt about the ambition, objectives, impacts, methodologies and concepts of each initiative showcased.

[WATCH RECORDING](#)

JOINT HANDBOOK

THE IMPORTANCE OF EUROPE

LEADING THE WAY IN TURNING CO₂ EMISSIONS INTO CHEMICALS

Horizon 2020
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13.7 Website

As a living platform, the website has evolved from M19 to M29 to include all the relevant actions, news, articles and relevant documents developed within the CATCO2NVERS framework.

Regarding the News section, in the last year twenty blog posts have been published:

- [INTERVIEW WITH TOM EWING – WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH](#)
- [UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE SHOWCASES THE CATCO2NVERS PROJECT IN SEVERAL EVENTS AND CONFERENCES](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS ATTENDS THE SECAT 2023 IN SPAIN](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS SHOWCASED DURING THE UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE OPEN HOUSE 2023](#)
- [THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL AND CATCO2NVERS](#)
- [EUROPE DAY: COMMEMORATING THE HISTORIC SCHUMAN DECLARATION](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS AT THE ADDING VALUE TO CO2 CONFERENCE](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS, THE PROGRESS AFTER TWO YEARS OF RUNNING](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH PABLO MORALES, COMMUNICATIONS MANAGER AT SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS PRESENTED AT THE CONFERENCE ON CO2-BASED FUELS & CHEMICALS 2023](#)
- [LEADING THE WAY IN TURNING CO2 EMISSIONS INTO CHEMICALS, THE RELATED PROJECTS WEBINAR ORGANISED BY CATCO2NVERS, VIVALDI AND CO2SMOS](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS PRESENTED DURING A STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE ON THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH MARCOS LATORRE, PERSEO](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS AT THE VIII INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR OF BIOPLASTICS AND SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH OSCAR RAMIREZ, PROJECT COORDINATOR.](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS AND ITS FIRST REVIEW MEETING WITH THE RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS AT THE NVBMB FALL MEETING](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS AT THE PARTICIPATES AT THE 18TH AACHENER MEMBRAN KOLLOQUIUM](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH DULCE MUÑOZ, TECHNICAL COORDINATOR](#)
- [CATCO2NVERS HOLDS ITS SECOND GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN ISTANBUL](#)

Likewise, during this period the following documents have been uploaded to the CATCO2NVERS website:

CATCO₂NVERS

- [Newsletter 4](#)
- Newsletter 5 (as of September 11, 2023 this campaign has not been sent yet)
- [Joint Handbook: of Leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals](#)
- [Scientific Paper: Metal-free catalytic systems based on imidazolium chloride](#)

From M19 to M29 the CATCO₂NVERS website has gained around 2400 sessions with an average session duration of 02:94 minutes which means that the audience is very engaged with the content of the website.

Image 13.7.1: Website performance, Audience overview.

In the next image, detailed audience information is displayed where SIE can track relevant information such as the top three pages visited, language breakdown, country breakdown as well as the top devices used:

Image 13.7.2: Website performance, breakdowns.

13.8 Partners contribution

Apart from the activities listed previously in terms of conferences attended, events organised, campaign participation, and scientific publications, CATCO2NVERS partners have been also active on social media. LinkedIn posts have been shared from M19-M30 and the partners were very supportive in this area. Likewise, consortium members have also made different posts during M19-M30 about CATCO2NVERS plus reported the social media post from CATCO2NVERS social media channels.

Some partners have accounts on other media channels and they have disseminated the project as well over there. The full partner's contribution is listed in the dissemination tables (Annex 1).

ANNEX 1: DISSEMINATION TABLES (M1-M30)

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

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TYPE OF ACTIVITY	MAIN LEADER / AUTHORS	TITLE	DATE	PLACE	TOTAL NUMBER OF STAKEHOLDERS	LINK	FLYERS DISTRIBUTED	OPEN ACCESS
FUNDTIC								
EVENT	DULCE MUÑOZ	FTECO2	22/05/2021	MADRID	100	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	NO
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	DOCUMENTS SECTION	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	403	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	4 EUROPEAN PROJECTS	JULY 2021	TWITTER	240	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	4 EUROPEAN PROJECTS	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	403	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	CATCO2NVERS IMPACTS	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	403	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	CATCO2NVERS IMPACTS	JULY 2021	TWITTER	238	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	415	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	CATCO2NVERS ON TWITTER	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	415	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	NOVA INSTITUTE INTERVIEW	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	415	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REWEET	FUNDTIC	FOLLOW CATCO2NVERS	AUGUST 2021	TWITTER	240	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	OSCAR RAMIREZ	CATCO2NVERS PRESENTATION	SEPTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	168	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	DULCE MUÑOZ	M4 CIRCARNIGHT	SEPTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	85 TEAM	SEPTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	445	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REWEET	FUNDTIC	1ST NEWSLETTER	SEPTEMBER 2021	TWITTER	243	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	OSCAR RAMIREZ	85S NEWSLETTER	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	168	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	FTECO2	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	475	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	DULCE MUÑOZ	INTERVIEW AVA	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	INTERVIEW AVA	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	475	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	GA MEETINGS	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	247	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	NO	YES
social media post	Fundtic	Interview ava	October 2021	twitter	243	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	no	yes
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	FTECO2	OCTOBER 2021	twitter	243	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	no	yes
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	FUNDTIC	GA MEETINGS	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	491	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SHARE SOCIAL MEDIA POST	DULCE MUÑOZ	GA MEETINGS	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	LEO BAKELAND	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	491	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REWEET	FUNDTIC	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	246	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	NO	YES
REWEET	FUNDTIC	END GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	246	https://twitter.com/Fundtic	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	DOCUMENTS SECTION	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	503	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	PREVIEW VIDEO	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	AVANTUM INTERVIEW	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	END OF 2021	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	END OF 2021	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	509	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	RELATED PROJECTS COLLABORATION	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	526	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	WOMEN IN SCIENCE	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	526	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	WOMEN IN SCIENCE	MARCH 2022	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	WOMEN IN SCIENCE	MARCH 2022	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
POST	FUNDTIC	NEW EMPLOYEE	MARCH 2022	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	GA MEETINGS	APRIL 2022	LINKEDIN	530	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	CATCO2NVERS AFTER 1 YEAR	may-22	LINKEDIN	550	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
POST	ECHEVERRI	IC2022	JUNE 2022	LINKEDIN	178	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
EVENT	ECHEVERRI	IC2022	JUNE 2022	VALENCIA, SPAIN	491	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	FUNDTIC	FUNDTIC CONFERENCE WITH CSIC	JULY 2022	TWITTER	428	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
POST	FUNDTIC	CONFERENCE ADVANCED MATERIALS	JULY 2022	TWITTER	271	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
CONFERENCE	FUNDTIC	CONFERENCE ADVANCED MATERIALS	JULY 2022	PORTUGAL	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	EUROPE DAY	nov-22	LINKEDIN	180	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	MARCELO ECHEVERRY	CATCO2NVERS VIDEO	nov-22	LINKEDIN	550	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	FUNDTIC INTERVIEW	dic-22	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	REVIEW MEETING BRUSSELS	ene-22	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SEMINAR	DULCE MUÑOZ & EVA MAYA	CONFERENCE	mar-23	AMSTERDAM	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
ORAL PRESENTATION	DULCE MUÑOZ	CONFERENCE	abr-23	COLOGNE	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
ORAL PRESENTATION	DULCE MUÑOZ	CONFERENCE	may-23	BILBAO	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	PAPER CSIC	MARCH 2023	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	JOINT WEBINAR	MARCH 2023	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	MARCELO ECHEVERRY	CONFERENCE FUELS CHEMICALS 2023	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	DULCE MUÑOZ	CONFERENCE FUELS CHEMICALS 2023	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
POST	FUNDTIC	MEETECH EVENT	01/05/2023	LINKEDIN	1157	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
EVENT	FUNDTIC	MEETECH EVENT	may-23	MADRID	1157	https://www.meetech.es/	YES	NO
CSIC								
SHARE CATCO2NVERS POST	EVA MAYA	INTERVIEW WITH AVA	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	248	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SHARE CATCO2NVERS POST	EVA MAYA	GA MEETINGS	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	250	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
GENERAL ASSEMBLY+ SUSTAINABLE PLASTICS	EVA MAYA	M4 STARTUP GROUP PRESENTATION	OCTOBER 2021	CSIC CENTRAL (MADRID)	150	http://www.epbc.csic.es/	NO	NO
PLENARY TALK	EVA MAYA	CATALADORÉS HETEROGÉNEOS BASADOS EN POLÍMEROS POROSOS ORGÁNICOS PARA CONVERSIÓN DE CO2 en carbonatos cíclicos (By Eva Maya)	DECEMBER 2021	CHILE (4ID Congress Play)	100	https://play.4id.science/	NO	NO
REPOST	EVA MAYA	GA POST	APRIL 2022	LINKEDIN	250	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
ORAL PRESENTATION in a Conference	EVA MAYA	Synthesis, characterization and catalytic performance of iron phthalocyanine based knitting aryl polymer	9th May 2022	KURSAL (SAN SEBASTIAN)	400	https://www.gop-ibp2022.org/	NO	NO
Outreach Activity	BETARIZ FUERTE	European Project	10th May 2022	MADRID	55	https://www.como-csic.es/	NO	YES
ORAL PRESENTATION in a Conference	ELIZABETH RANGEL	Indidazolium-based hypercrosslinked ionic polymer to promote the oxidative esterification of furfural	11 th May 2022	KURSAL (SAN SEBASTIAN)	400	https://www.gop-ibp2022.org/	NO	NO
SEMINAR	EVA MAYA	Thermal conversions of CO2 using Porous Organic Polymers	12th May 2012	MATERIAL PHYSICS CENTER (SAN SEBASTIAN)	20	https://cfm.ehu.es/	YES	YES
CONFERENCE WITH RELATED PROJECT in FUNDTIC	EVA MAYA	CONFERENCE WITH RELATED PROJECT in FUNDTIC	JUNE 2022	FUNDTIC	26	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	NO
Outreach Activity	BETARIZ FUERTE	THESIS	10th May 2022	55	https://www.como-csic.es/	NO	YES	
ORAL PRESENTATION in a Conference	ELIZABETH RANGEL	Indidazolium-based hypercrosslinked ionic polymer to promote the oxidative esterification of furfural	11 th May 2022	400	https://www.gop-ibp2022.org/	NO	NO	
SEMINAR	EVA MAYA	Thermal conversions of CO2 using Porous Organic Polymers	12th May 2012	20	https://cfm.ehu.es/	YES	YES	
INDUSTRY DAY	EVA MAYA	Sustainable solutions to scientific and industrial problems	16th June 2022	60	https://www.sustlab-csic.es/	NO	NO	
CATALYSTS WORKSHOP	EVA MAYA	Sistemas catalíticos optimizados para reacciones de esterificación oxidativa	20th June 2022	15	NO	NO	NO	
REPOST	CSIC	FUNDTIC INTERVIEW	FEBRUARY 2023	LINKEDIN	145	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	EVA MAYA	PAPER CSIC	MARCH 2023	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	EVA MAYA	JOINT WEBINAR	may-23	LINKEDIN	256	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	EVA MAYA	EUROPE DAY CSIC	may-23	LINKEDIN	256	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
EVENT	CSIC	EUROPE DAY CSIC	may-23	MADRID	50	https://europe.day.csic.es/	NO	YES
REPOST	EVA MAYA	EUROPE DAY CSIC	may-23	LINKEDIN	150	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	ELIZABETH RANGEL	INTERVIEW IIR	may-23	LINKEDIN	150	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	ELIZABETH RANGEL	COMMUNICATION MATERIALS	may-23	LINKEDIN	150	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	ELIZABETH RANGEL	GA VALLADOLID	may-23	LINKEDIN	150	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
POSTER PRESENTATION	EVA MAYA & DULCE MIÑOZ	Presentation of thermocatalytic technologies of CATCO2NVERS	1-2 March 2023	VALENCIA	100	https://ehsbot.org/evencia/	NO	NO
POSTER PRESENTATION	EVA MAYA	Presentation of other CO2 conversion using catalysts developed at CATCO2NVERS	9-10 May 2023	BILBAO	60	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	NO
EVENT	BETARIZ FUERTE	Brief presentation of CATCO2NVERS- Video display	9th May 2023	MADRID	40	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REPOST	ELIZABETH RANGEL	WHAT IS A BIOBASED INDUSTRY?	JULY 2023	LINKEDIN	150	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
WUOL								
Shared LinkedIn post	WR	CATCO2NVERS announcement	01/04/2021	LinkedIn	540	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
Webpage on institute website (in Dutch)	WR	Project summary	14/12/2021	Website	540	https://www.gop-ibp.nl/en/About	NO	YES
Lightning talk and poster presentation of conference	WR	Biocatalytic conversion of industrial off-gas carbon dioxide to commodity chemicals	31/08/2022	BioCat2022, Hamburg	350	https://www.biocat-conference.com/	YES	YES
REPOST	DAAN M. VAN VLIET	CATCO2NVERS OBJECTIVES	AUGUST 2022	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
Poster presentation	WR	Biocatalytic conversion of industrial off-gas carbon dioxide to commodity chemicals	12/05/2022	NVBB&B fall meeting 2022			YES	NO
CARTIF								
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	CARIF	PRESS RELEASE KOM	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	5499	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	CARIF	KOM ONE MONTH AGO	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	5547	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	CARIF	CARTIF WEB NEWS	JULY 2021	TWITTER	3115	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
WEB POST	CARIF	CARTIF WEB NEWS	JULY 2021	CARTIF WEBSITE		https://www.cartif.es/en/Carif	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	CARIF	CARTIF WEB NEWS	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	5000	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	CARIF	CARTIF WEB NEWS	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	5000	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
REWEET	CARIF	CO2ONE LAYER DAY	SEPTEMBER 2021	TWITTER	3190	https://twitter.com/CartifNL	NO	YES
POST	CARIF	WEB POST	MARCH 2022	TWITTER	3387	https://twitter.com/CartifNL	NO	YES
POST	CARIF	WEB NEW ABOUT CATCO2NVERS	JULY 2022	TWITTER	3521	https://twitter.com/CartifNL	NO	YES
WEB POST	CARIF	ABOUT CATCO2NVERS	JULY 2022	TWITTER		https://www.cartif.es/about	NO	YES

Project	Activity	Category	Date	Status	Views	URL	Platform	Yes/No	
HVSYTECH	SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	PRESS RELEASE KOM	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	1572	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	KOM	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	1572	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	POSTDAY KOM	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	1572	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	PRESS RELEASE	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	1572	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	SOME MEDIA POST ABOUT CATCOZNVERS	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	1572	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	WEBST	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	1572	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	SOCIAL MEDIA DAY	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	1572	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE TWITTER POST	HYVSYTECH	CA12 IREAI KOM	JUNE 2021	TWITTER	183	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
SHARE TWITTER POST	HYVSYTECH	CA12 IREAI KOM	JUNE 2021	TWITTER	183	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
SHARE TWITTER POST	HYVSYTECH	CA12 gmsi (sistem)	JUNE 2021	TWITTER	183	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
SHARE TWITTER POST	HYVSYTECH	CA12 website	JUNE 2021	TWITTER	183	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	DOCUMENTS SECTION	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	1428	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	CATCOZNVERS IMPACTS	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	1654	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	ODONE LAYER DAY	SEPTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	1680	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	INTERVIEW AVA	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	1751	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	HYVSYTECH	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	247	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	HYVSYTECH	PRECO	OCTOBER 2021	Twitter	247	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	GA ASSEMBLY	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	1751	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	HYVSYTECH	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	1783	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REWEET	HYVSYTECH	END OF GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	193	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REWEET	HYVSYTECH	INTERVIEW ALC	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	192	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REWEET	HYVSYTECH	HYVSYTECH RESULTS	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	192	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REWEET	HYVSYTECH	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	192	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	DOCUMENTS SECTION	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	1810	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	PREVIEW VIDEO	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	1810	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	RELATED PROJECTS MEETING SOON	JANUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	1938	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	WOMEN IN SCIENCE	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	2032	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	SUBPLANT EVENT	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	2032	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	BIOECONOMY EVENT	MARCH 2022	LINKEDIN	2096	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	GA M12 CATCOZNVERS	APRIL 2022	LINKEDIN	2158	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	HYVSYTECH	DISCOVERING EUROPEAN PROJECTS	may-25	LINKEDIN	2158	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	THE PROGRESS AFTER ONE YEAR OF RUNNING	may-22	LINKEDIN	2158	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	COAGOFARME EXHIBITION 2022	may-22	LINKEDIN	2158	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	HYVSYTECH	DISCOVERING EUROPEAN PROJECTS	may-22	LINKEDIN	201	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	NEW MILESTONE	JULY 2022	LINKEDIN	2254	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	BIOTECH CONFERENCE	JULY 2022	LINKEDIN	2254	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	OBJECTIVES CATCOZNVERS	AUGUST 2022	LINKEDIN	2326	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	MILESTONE	AUGUST 2022	LINKEDIN	2326	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	SOGL	AUGUST 2022	LINKEDIN	2326	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	BIOCAT 2022	sep-22	LINKEDIN	2372	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	LINKEDIN	GA M18	oct-22	LINKEDIN	2424	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	LINKEDIN	ECOMONDO22	nov-22	LINKEDIN	2543	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
CONFERENCE	LINKEDIN	ECOMONDO22	nov-22	ITALY		https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	VIDEO CATCO	nov-22	LINKEDIN	2543	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	BIOTECH INTERVIEW	dec-22	LINKEDIN	2666	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	DISCOVERING REVIEW	23-sep	LINKEDIN	2756	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	REVIEW MEETING	23-sep	LINKEDIN	2750	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	WEB POST REVIEW MEETING	February 2023	LINKEDIN	2800	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	CO2 RESEARCH	MARCH 2023	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	JOINT WEBINAR	MARCH 2023	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	JOINT HANDBOOK	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	WEBINAR RECORDING	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	BIOTECHNOLOGY DIALOGUE	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	FUELS AND CHEMICALS CONFERENCE	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	ALEXANDRU MOROSANU	may-23	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	GA VALLADOLID	may-23	LINKEDIN	349	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	FREDDY LERDO	may-23	LINKEDIN	349	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	HYVSYTECH	JOINT WEBINAR	may-23	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	HYVSYTECH	COMMUNICATION MATERIALS	may-23	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	INTERVIEW SE	may-23	LINKEDIN	2900	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	GA ASSEMBLY WEB POST	JUNE 2023	LINKEDIN	3000	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	WEB POST ABOUT CO2 CONFERENCE	JUNE 2023	LINKEDIN	3000	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	OPEN DAYS U TWENTIE	JUNE 2023	LINKEDIN	3000	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	WHAT IS A BIOSSECTOR	JULY 2023	LINKEDIN	3100	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL POST	JULY 2023	LINKEDIN	3100	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	HYVSYTECH	CATCOZNVERS POSTER	AUGUST 2023	LINKEDIN	3170	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	YES	
EMI	SHARE LINKEDIN POST	EMI	PRESS RELEASE KOM	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	752	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	EMI	LINKEDIN	SEPTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	758	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	EMI	LINKEDIN	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	880	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	EMI	LINKEDIN	44835	LINKEDIN	962	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Shared in conference	EMI	ANAL ASSOCIATE Membership Kolbium	44835	LINKEDIN	150	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	EMI	GA VALLADOLID	45047	LINKEDIN	1116	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	NO	
POST	EMI	ICOM 2023	45047	LINKEDIN	1138	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	NO	
EVENT	EMI	ICOM2023	JULY 2023	TWITTER		https://twitter.com/hyvstech	YES	NO	
AVANTIUM	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KRASOVIC	CATCOZNVERS PRESS RELEASE	JUNE	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
PRESS RELEASE	AVT	Avantium awarded €1.78 million in total from EU grants for the development of electrochemical processes and CO2-based polymers	MAY	AVT WEBSITE		https://www.avantium.com/	NO	YES	
Training&Dissemination event	Mariana Paredinha Araujo [AVT]	CO2ing the Earth Summer School (3rd edition)	44467	Online event		https://co2ingearth.eu/	NO	YES	
Event	Mariana Paredinha Araujo [AVT]	InfTech2022 - Conference on Industrial Technologies	27/04/2022	Grenoble	300	https://www.inftech2022.com/	NO	NO	
PERSEO	SHARE LINKEDIN POST	PERSEO	PRESS RELEASE	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	773	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	PERSEO	KOM	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	773	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	PERSEO	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	922	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
EVENT	PERSEO	INNOV4UM 2021	NOVEMBER 2021	Hybrid format (Online/Face-to-face of universities)	300	https://www.innov4um.com/	NO	YES	
POST	PERSEO	FACE OF THE 2021	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	995	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	PERSEO	BIOECONOMY EVENT	MARCH 2022	LINKEDIN	1051	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	PERSEO	GA VALLADOLID	may-23	LINKEDIN	1400	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
DANNA	Shared POST	DANNA	PRESS RELEASE	23/04/2021	LINKEDIN	518	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES
Shared POST	DANNA	WEBSITE LAUNCH	29/04/2021	LINKEDIN	555	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Shared POST	DANNA	Aziuladoddi RETEMA NEWS	27/05/2021	LINKEDIN	556	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Shared POST	NATHALIE	WEBSITE LAUNCH	27/06/2021	LINKEDIN	1380	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Re-Shared POST	NATHALIE	Aziuladoddi RETEMA NEWS	27/05/2021	LINKEDIN	1350	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Shared POST	NATHALIE	KOM	08/04/2021	LINKEDIN	1350	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Shared POST	NATHALIE	KOM Assogestioni	07/04/2021	LINKEDIN	1350	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Retweet	DANNA	WEBSITE LAUNCH	24/04/2021	TWITTER	3394	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
Retweet	DANNA	Aziuladoddi RETEMA NEWS	14/05/2021	TWITTER	3394	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	XAVIER MARRIN	SOCIAL MEDIA DAY	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	18266	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	XAVIER MARRIN	KOM ONE MONTH AGO	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	18266	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	DANNA	PRECO EVENT	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	588	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REWEET	DANNA	REWEET CARIEF CATCOZNVERS NEWS	JULY 2021	TWITTER	403	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	NATHALIE	KOM ONE MONTH AGO	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	1389	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	NATHALIE	WEBSITE LAUNCH	JULY 2021	LINKEDIN	1389	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REWEET	NATHALIE	REWEET CATCOZNVERS	AUGUST 2021	TWITTER	51	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REPOST	NATHALIE	REPOST CATCOZNVERS	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	1389	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REWEET	NATHALIE	REWEET CATCOZNVERS newsletter	AUGUST 2021	TWITTER	51	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REPOST	NATHALIE	NOVA INTERVIEW	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	1389	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	REPOST CATCOZNVERS	sepTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	753	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	REPOST CATCOZNVERS	sepTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	753	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REWEET	DANNA	REWEET Inf CATcozn Newsletter	sepTEMBER 2021	TWITTER	3394	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REWEET	NATHALIE	REWEET INTERNATIONAL DAY FOR THE PRESERVATION OF THE OZONE LAYER	SEPTEMBER 2021	TWITTER	51	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REPOST	NATHALIE	NEWSLETTER RELEASE	SEPTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	1427	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	DANNA	MIDDLE DAY	OCTOBER 2021	LINKEDIN	791	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	DANNA	PRECO	OCTOBER 2021	Twitter	3398	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	821	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REWEET	DANNA	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	3394	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
TWEET	NATHALIE	GA MEETING IN MADRID - LIVE	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	55	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REWEET	NATHALIE	GA MEETING	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	55	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REWEET	NATHALIE	LEO BAKELAND - BAKELITA INVENTION - FIRST PLASTIC SUBSTANCE	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	55	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	PREVIEW VIDEO	DECEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	895	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REWEET	NATHALIE	EXPLORING COLLABORATIONS BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES	JANUARY 2022	TWITTER	56	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REPOST	NATHALIE	OFFICIAL VIDEO	JANUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	412	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	OFFICIAL VIDEO	JANUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	1016	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	XAVIER MARRIN	OFFICIAL VIDEO	JANUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
EVENT	DANNA	SUBPLANT EVENT	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	1086	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	NATHALIE	INTERNATIONAL DAY OF WOMEN AND GIRLS IN SCIENCE	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	289	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	DANNA	OFFICIAL VIDEO	MARCH 2022	LINKEDIN	1131	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	DANNA	OFFICIAL VIDEO	MARCH 2022	TWITTER	3385	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
POST	NATHALIE	SECOND NEWSLETTER	MARCH 2022	LINKEDIN		https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	GA IMAGES	APRIL 2022	TWITTER	3379	https://twitter.com/hyvstech	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	GA IMAGES	APRIL 2022	LINKEDIN	1217	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	CATCOZNVERS AFTER 1 YEAR	may-22	LINKEDIN	1280	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	COAGOFARMA 2022	may-22	LINKEDIN	1280	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	DANNA	INTERVIEW DANNA	AUGUST 2022	LINKEDIN	1588				

NOVA									
SHARE CATCOZNVERS POST	DOMINIK VOGT	NOVA INTERVIEW	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE CATCOZNVERS POST	ALCHEMIA NOVA	THE PROGRESS AFTER 1 YEAR	01/05/2022	LINKEDIN	822	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SE									
POST	SE	PRESS RELEASE	27/05/2021	LINKEDIN	5619	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	PRESS RELEASE	28/05/2021	TWITTER	652	https://twitter.com/AlchemiaNova	NO	YES	
POST	SE	KOM	08/04/2021	LINKEDIN	5723	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	KOM	09/04/2021	TWITTER	452	https://twitter.com/AlchemiaNova	NO	YES	
POST	SE	EMPLOYEE POST: COMM. MGR	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	5852	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA MEETINGS	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	6125	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA MEETINGS	NOVEMBER 2021	TWITTER	6125	https://twitter.com/AlchemiaNova	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA MEETINGS	NOVEMBER 2021	INSTAGRAM	6125	https://www.instagram.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA MEETING M12	APRIL 2022	TWITTER	730	https://twitter.com/AlchemiaNova	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA MEETING M12	APRIL 2022	INSTAGRAM	579	https://www.instagram.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA MEETING M12	APRIL 2022	LINKEDIN	4591	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA M1B	oct-22	TWITTER	759	https://twitter.com/AlchemiaNova	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA M1B	22-oct	LINKEDIN	7185	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA M1B	22-oct	INSTAGRAM	759	https://www.instagram.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	REVIEW MEETING BRUSSELS	ene-23	TWITTER	775	https://twitter.com/AlchemiaNova	NO	YES	
POST	SE	REVIEW MEETING BRUSSELS	ene-23	INSTAGRAM	581	https://www.instagram.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	REVIEW MEETING BRUSSELS	ene-23	LINKEDIN	7400	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	SE	JOINT WEBINAR	MARCH 2023	LINKEDIN	7500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	PABLO MORALES	JOINT WEBINAR	MARCH 2023	LINKEDIN	7500	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	SE	WE ARE LEVEL WEBINAR	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	7400	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA VALLADOLID	may-23	LINKEDIN	7800	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA VALLADOLID	may-23	TWITTER	1100	https://twitter.com/AlchemiaNova	NO	YES	
POST	SE	GA VALLADOLID	may-23	INSTAGRAM	500	https://www.instagram.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	PABLO MORALES	INTERVIEW SE	may-23	LINKEDIN	800	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
ALC									
website post	Alchemia-nova	Product description on website	June 2021	ALC website		https://www.alchemia-nova.com/	NO	YES	
linkedin post	Alchemia-nova	Report & promotion of CATCOZNVERS newsletter	August 2021	LinkedIn	591	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
facebook post	Alchemia-nova	promotion of CATCOZNVERS newsletter	August 2021	FACEBOOK	908	https://www.facebook.com/	NO	YES	
SOCIAL MEDIA POST	ALCHEMIA NOVA	SUBSCRIBE TO CATCOZNVERS NEWSLETTER	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	588	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE CATCOZNVERS POST	ALCHEMIA NOVA	NOVA INTERVIEW	NOVEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	442	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	ALCHEMIA NOVA	OFFICIAL VIDEO	JANUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	681	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	IRIS DE CÉSARE	GA M1B	oct-22	LINKEDIN	800	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	ALCHEMIA NOVA	JOINT HANDBOOK	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	1230	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	ALCHEMIA NOVA	STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE	APRIL 2023	LINKEDIN	1200	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	IRIS DE CÉSARE	GA VALLADOLID	may-23	LINKEDIN	302	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
REPOST	IRIS DE CÉSARE	WHAT IS A BIOMIMETIC INDUSTRY?	JULY 2023	LINKEDIN	302	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
EVYAP									
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	ASU OZGE	KOM ONE MONTH AGO	JUNE 2021	LINKEDIN	527	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	ASU OZGE	PUBLIC DELIVERABLE 7.1	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	527	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	ASU OZGE	CATCOZNVERS IMPACTS	AUGUST 2021	LINKEDIN	527	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	ASU OZGE	NOVA INTERVIEW	SEPTEMBER 2021	LINKEDIN	528	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	ASU OZGE	CATCOZNVERS VIDEO	JANUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	528	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
SHARE LINKEDIN POST	ASU OZGE	CATCOZNVERS VIDEO	FEBRUARY 2022	LINKEDIN	528	https://www.linkedin.com/	NO	YES	
Event	ASU OZGE	Beauty & Care Exhibition 2022	12-20/03/2022	ISTANBUL	20000	http://beautyandcare.com/	YES	NO	
Event	ASU OZGE	Cosmofarma 2022	04.05.2022 - 08.05.2022	Bologna	15000	https://www.cosmofarma.it/	YES	YES	
Event	ASU OZGE	CosmeticBusiness 2022	01.06.2022 - 02.06.2022	München	2000	https://tr.vadefair.cosmetic.biz/	YES	YES	
Event	ASU OZGE	BeautyEurasia 2022	15.04.2022 - 17.04.2022	Istanbul	10000	https://www.beautyeurasia.com/	YES	YES	
Event	ASU OZGE	Exhibition BEAUTYISTANBUL - Exhibition for Cosmetics, Beauty, Hair, Private Label, Home Care, Packaging, Ingredients 2022	13.10.2022 - 15.10.2022	Istanbul	3000	https://beautyistanbul.com/	YES	YES	
Event	ASU OZGE	Perfumes & Cosmetics Congress 2022	23.11.2022 - 24.11.2022	Chartres, France	20000	http://www.congres.parfums.com/	YES	YES	
REPOST	ASU OZGE	GA M12	APRIL 2022	LINKEDIN	694	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	NO	
REPOST	ASU OZGE	GA M1B	oct-22	LINKEDIN	700	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	NO	
REPOST	ASU OZGE	END OF 2022	dic-22	LINKEDIN	700	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	NO	
REPOST	ASU OZGE	CATCOZNVERS POSTER	AUGUST 2023	LINKEDIN	700	https://www.linkedin.com/	YES	YES	